

LINGUOCULTURAL ANALYSIS OF THE CONCEPT “HEALTH” IN ENGLISH AND RUSSIAN LANGUAGES

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Annotation: The paper contains an analysis of origin of the word «health» in linguistic branches of Indo-European stem. Health is a lasting value of universal type, but the content and actualization of peculiar features of the concept is different. During comparison between figurative meanings of the concept of «health» a similarity between the Russian and English languages is discovered, though there are some differences. The found ethnocultural specific features are caused by different development levels of each of the analyzed culture and different view of the world.

Key words: figurative meaning, influence, ethnoculture, origin, differentiate, notion, actualization, consciousness, disease.

The concept of «health» comprises complex structured mental formations that include notional, figurative, and value features, partially coinciding and differing in various linguocultures. The paper contains an analysis of origin of the word «health» in linguistic branches of Indo-European stem. It is found that the origin and meaning of the word «здоровье» (health), fixed in the Russian language, is older, than the meaning of health as an «integrity of all systems of the organism», fixed in the Roman and Germanic linguistic branches. Health is a lasting value of universal type, but the content and actualization of peculiar features of the concept is different. During comparison between figurative meanings of the concept of «health» a similarity between the Russian and English languages is discovered (health is the most important value, influence of Christian traditions), though there are some differences. The found ethnocultural specific

features are caused by different development levels of each of the analyzed culture and different view of the world. Health is a common category enduring interest but the nature and actualization of the concept's peculiar features are different. A similiarity between the Russian and English languages is discovered during the contrast between figurative interpretations of the definition of "health" (health is the most important attribute, influence of Christian traditions), though there are some variations. There are currently more than a hundred interpretations of the notion of health in the scientific literature, which represent approaches from various sciences. Health is a fundamental concept and has a significant importance for the whole of human life. Health in all social types, modes of religion, various nationalities are among the best, absolute the best, historically defined values. It is triggered by a certain human organization, in particular a sense of self-protection which is characteristic of all flesh. [1;p.21]

Nonetheless, the importance of health among different nations was different at different times. Health definitions evolved with a shift in civilizations, traditions, epochs, methods of development. Physical health was very important in primitive society because it was physical health that determined whether this or that individual would survive. As more complicated production and more complex organization of social interactions appeared, a value formation process changed. The ideals acquired abstract and general character. The language like a mirror, represents all the basic features of those conceptions. The definition of "health" is one of the important guidelines of the human vital and acquires various lexical and phraseological designations in the language. The papers goal is undertake a linguocultural study of the concept study of the concept "health" in different national cultures. We assume that an account of the interaction between language and culture would allow us to differentiate between the notion, figurative and value features of the concept of "health, partially coinciding and differing in various linguocultures. We will take the definition of concept, given by Maslova V.A. in accordance to which "concept is a semantic formation, marked by linguocultural

specific features and characterizing bearers of a certain ethnoculture which is surrounded by an emotional, expressive, evaluating halo”. [2:p.36] The concept of health is an abstract one. It is not a concrete object, which one is able to see, hear, or touch. But people perceive its importance through figurative concepts, consider health as a valuable thing – wealth, treasure, gold.

Table 1 presents notional, figurative, and value features of the concept of «health» in the Russian, English linguocultures.

Table 1 Analysis of features of the concept of «health» in various linguocultures.

Feature	Russian language	English language
Health as a value	Health in the Russian national consciousness is the most important value, which is put higher than material goods. Health is the best wealth, Health is more expensive than gold, Health is more expensive than money, One cannot buy health. The ethno-specific features are: «normal condition of the organism», «social health», «strong, solid built», «nimble, artful».	A physiological human condition is accepted the most important aspect in his or her life. Health is understood as integrity of the organism, sustainability of its functioning. Healthy mind in a healthy body. He who has health has hope, and he who has hope has everything. Health is better than wealth. The ethno-specific features are: “degree of success”, “happiness”, “the work of providing medical services”.

<p>Health as a sense of moderation</p>	<p>The Russian proverbial stock inculcates a necessity to observe such habits as neatness, cold training, moving activity, refusal to bad habits, moderation in food and drinks. Moderation is the mother of health. Move more – will live longer. Lie after lunch, walk after dinner.</p> <p>health</p>	<p>In the English language the importance of moderation for one's health is also emphasized. Besides, the connection between good mood and health is pointed out. Temperance is the best physic. To lengthen thy (=your) life, lessen thy (=your) meals. Health and cheerfulness mutually beget each other.</p>
<p>Health as a good, gift from above</p>	<p>Health is a basis for happiness, gives an opportunity to live and work completely. Health is a gift from God, which may transfer into a harm. Then, from the viewpoint of the Russian Orthodox religion, God gives a disease to the human for correction («to show patience, to clean from passions»).</p>	<p>In the English linguoculture health is mostly associated with medical notions, as well as with medical institutions, in addition, with natural resources as a means of diseases prevention. Perhaps, that is the reason why the word «wellness» acquired its place in the modern language, which is used to designate the condition of physical and spiritual</p>

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To sum up, the performed linguoculturological study of the concept of “ health”,it can be concluded the feature of the given term in different cultures are very similar. Nonetheless, it is also possible to discern the ethnonational basic characteristics, induced by people’s mindset, macroeconomic, landscape-natural, and other health experience connotations.

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